

Standardization of Plant Material: A Key Role of Phytoproduct Development

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Received: January 22, 2014, Accepted: January 28, 2014, Published: January 31, 2014.

Medicinal plants are normally used in their crude forms in traditional medicines. They may be employed in the forms of fresh or dried plant parts, plant exudates, juices, gums, fixed oil or volatile oils [1]. The quality of a plant depends on various parameters such as genetic variation; environmental conditions under which it is grown e.g. soil fertility, moisture, temperature, length of growing season, time of harvest; and dry processing [2].

The evaluation of crude drug, which eventually enters the commercial market, is of paramount importance. The quality assessment of crude plant material should include correct identification of a plant; giving a description and an indication of plant part used; specification of active constituents and content limits; limitation of foreign matters, impurities, and microbial content; and voucher specimen storage condition [1].

The concentration of active constituents in different batches of plant material is highly variable. For example, turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.) cultivated in various parts of Thailand contains different contents of turmeric oil and curcuminoids. The highest content (8.2% v/w) of essential oil was found in dried samples from the North where the climate is cool, while the lowest oil content (7% v/w) was found in the samples from the South where it rains all year. In contrast, the highest total curcuminoids content (9% dry weight) was found in the southern samples while the lowest content (4.9% dry weight) was in the northern samples [3].

Standardization of plant raw material and plant extracts extremely important in the field of phyto-medicinal product development. Assurance of the safety, quality, and efficacy of medicinal plants and their products become a key issue in many countries [4]. The most effective way to assure herbal quality is to assay the amount of active constituents in the plant/plant extract. If an active chemical constituent is known, they can be isolated, identified, and quantified by appropriate physical or chemical methods. If the active substance of the plant is not known, other major components can be used to characterize the plant as a marker for quality control. In the case where active and major compounds are unknown or it is a complex mixture, a biological assay should be performed. When the potency of the plant/plant

extract is known, it can be mixed appropriately with other additives to formulate a product with a defined activity [2].

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